

Early Jurassic and Late Cretaceous magmatism on Horseshoe Island, Antarctic Peninsula: New U-Pb and microstructural data

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Abstract. Early Jurassic U-Pb age is obtained for both foliated and undeformed granites on Horseshoe Island, Antarctic Peninsula. Some microstructures in the foliated granites/orthogneisses indicate high-temperature greenschist or low- to medium-temperature amphibolite facies deformation conditions. Additionally, a Late Cretaceous age is yielded for a gabbro intruding the deformed granitoids.

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INTRODUCTION

Horseshoe Island is a part of the Marguerite Bay archipelago on the west coast of the Graham Land, northern Antarctic Peninsula. Broadly, the West Antarctic region records a complex active continental margin setting and extensive magmatism since the early Mesozoic, with peaks during ~184–180 Ma and ~118–110 Ma (e.g., Bastias Silva, 2020), including magmatic arc development, as well as fore-arc and back-arc successions evidencing both subduction along the proto-Pacific margin of Gondwa-

na and rifting in the Weddell Sea sector (e.g., Jordan *et al.*, 2020). Despite the small size of the island (~60 km²), its local geology is complex. On the only available geological map, Matthews (1983) distinguished a complex of foliated granites and banded gneisses (Basement Complex or Antarctic Peninsula Metamorphic Complex), suite of pre-Jurassic (?) granites, a Jurassic volcano-sedimentary sequence (Antarctic Peninsula Volcanic Group), and the Andean Plutonic Suite (gabbro-diorite-granite) and co-genetic dykes (Fig. 1). Such subdivision is quite general because of the lack of any known fos-

siliferous varieties, as well as the presence of huge masses of crystalline rocks, for which only scattered geochronological data exists.

Herein, we present field, petrographic and U-Pb zircon data from foliated and isotropic granites from the basement, as well as gabbro, which intruded them. The obtained results are important in the further revision of the map, restoring of the structural evolution of the area, and correlation with the adjacent regions of the Antarctic Peninsula.

GEOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

After the pioneering work of Matthews (1983), only a few geochronological studies provided information about the ages of some of the rock units comprising the island. Protolith age of ~270 Ma was obtained for a weakly foliated tonalite cutting amphibolites, and the high-grade metamorphic overprint was defined at 206 ± 4 Ma (Millar *et al.*, 2002). In a post-Permian highly sheared

Fig. 1. Geological sketch map of Horseshoe and Reluctant islands (after Matthews, 1983).

Gaul Cove conglomerate, Late Ordovician to Late Silurian and Late Permian protolith ages were reported for the variously foliated granitoid boulders (Tangeman *et al.*, 1996; Loske *et al.*, 1997, 1998). Data from the granitoid gneisses exposed at Reluctant Island, just east of Horseshoe Island (Fig. 1), point Early to Mid-Jurassic magmatic event (Loske *et al.*, 1997; Riley *et al.*, 2017). The Rb-Sr age of the sampled Antarctic Peninsula Volcanic Group at Homing Head is 121 ± 10 Ma (Loske *et al.*, 1997, 1998). Pink granite (Andean plutonic suite) at the northwestern Gaul Cove is ~ 107 – 108 Ma, and hornblende gabbro at Sally Cove is 73.6 ± 0.4 Ma (Tangeman *et al.*, 1996).

RESULTS

The field observations and sampling were carried out along a traverse from the eastern coast of Lystad Bay, along the eastern side of Mount Searle northwest of Gaul Cove (Fig. 1). A 1–2 km wide and 4 km long tract of variously foliated to undeformed granitoids is exposed, previously distinguished by Matthews (1983) as the Antarctic Peninsula Metamorphic Complex or “Basement Complex”. The foliation is generally NE–SW striking and nearly vertical. Most of the granitoids are pink or grayish, coarse-grained and K-feldspar phyrlic. The main rock-forming minerals are feldspars (K-feldspar \gg plagioclase) and quartz. Subordinate biotite and hornblende, and accessories – epidote, zircon, apatite and big (up to 1 mm long) euhedral crystals of allanite, are also present. An important indirect indicator of the deformation conditions of these rocks is the K-feldspar behavior. Many of the porphyroclasts are surrounded by thin (~ 0.1 – 0.2 mm) mantles of newly grown fine feldspars as the boundaries between the old grain and mantel are sharp and serrated. Fine micro-shear zones cut the cores of the old K-feldspars. Both structures suggest a deformation temperature in an interval between 450–600 °C (*e.g.*, Passchier and Trouw, 2005).

On the northeastern coast of Lystad Bay, the complex of foliated granites is intruded by gabbro, locally passing into gabbro-diorite and diorite – part of the Andean Plutonic Suite. These are medium- to coarse-grained rocks, locally pyroxene phyrlic. Both cumulate texture and rhythmic layering are locally observed in gabbro, suggesting a relatively slow rate of crystallization. The main rock-forming minerals are plagioclase, ortho- and clinopyroxene, and hornblende. A small quantity of biotite and quartz are

present in diorites. Hypidiomorphic-granular and ophitic structures are common as euhedral to subhedral plagioclase is partially or entirely included in subhedral to anhedral pyroxene and hornblende. In many cases, anhedral hornblende replaces or overgrows pyroxene.

Two samples of foliated granite (HI002 and HI011) and one of rather undeformed granite (HI008), as well as one of gabbro-diorite (HI007), were taken for geochronological and geochemical analyses. The mineral separation was performed at the Geological Engineering Department of Çukurova University, Adana, Turkey, and the LA-ICP-MS zircon U-Pb analyses at the Geological Processes Department of the Geology Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague (Czech Republic). Both samples of foliated granite/orthogneiss, as well as the undeformed granite yielded an Early Jurassic age (188–181 Ma), interpreted as a crystallization age of the granites. The gabbro-diorite is Late Cretaceous (77–75 Ma) in age.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The obtained Early Jurassic ages of the foliated and undeformed granitoids correspond well to the precise geochronology recently published by Karataş *et al.* (2023) and Riely *et al.* (2016). The data proves well the Early Jurassic stage of the magmatic activity, which seems widely presented on the island and the adjacent region. Nevertheless, the genesis of these igneous products and further deformation is still poorly studied. The observed microstructures in the sheared granitoids reflect high-temperature greenschist or low- to medium-temperature amphibolite facies deformation conditions, which could reflect both a late syn-magmatic or post-magmatic deformation. However, the process definitely predates the Late Cretaceous emplacement of the gabbro, whose age generally coincides with those obtained from a hornblende gabbro (Tangeman *et al.*, 1996) northwest of our sampling locality.

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